

Role of physico-chemical parameters in Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship based modeling of CYP26A1 inhibitory activity

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Abstract : Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) studies were performed on CYP26A1 inhibitory activity using physico-chemical parameters like Balaban centric index (BAC), mean Wiener index (WA), Balaban distance connectivity index (J), information theoretic index (Id), zero order ($^0\chi$), first order ($^1\chi$) and second order ($^2\chi$) of molecular connectivity, polarizability (Pz) and partition coefficient (log P) along with appropriate dummy parameter. The QSAR models were tested for their statistical significance and reliability by using leave one out cross validation method. Some significant models have been reported.

Keywords : QSAR, CYP26A1, physico-chemical parameters.

Introduction

CYP26A1 is found in the liver, heart, pituitary gland, adrenal gland, testis, brain and placenta¹ in human beings. CYP26A1 is homeostatic and it regulates the steady state levels of intracellular Anti Trans Retinoic Acid (ATRA) via a negative feed back loop. It is, therefore, very clear that CYP26A1 is the most important enzyme involved in the degradation² processes.

It is experimentally found that CYP26A1 is useful target in combating the development of resistance in treating cancer. Elevation of normal tissue levels of ATRA by inhibiting CYP26A1 or by maintaining high therapeutic levels of ATRA, more resistance power could easily be developed. The role of CYP26A1 analogues was investigated by S. Pautus and coworkers³ using MCF-7 cell-based assays and we have used the data as reported by them.

Results and discussion

The 2D structures of the molecules were drawn using Chem Sketch software. Several physico-chemical parameters were calculated for the present series³ such as BAC⁴, WA⁴, J⁴, Id⁵, $^0\chi$ ⁴, $^1\chi$ ⁴, $^2\chi$ ⁴, Pz⁶ and log P⁷, which have been found to be useful in QSAR based drug modeling⁸⁻²². Except log P, Id and Pz all physico-chemical

parameters were calculated with DRAGON software. We have calculated log P as suggested by Nys and Rekker⁷, Id by using the method of Lucic and Trinajstic⁵ and Pz by ACD-Lab chemsketch software. The indicator parameter IR₃ (=1) has also been used which accounts for the [-CH(CH₂CH₃)₂] group at R₃ position. Regression analysis was performed by using SPSS 7.5 version.

All the compounds of the series along with, calculated physico-chemical parameters are given in Table 1. In multiple regression analysis, the independent variables must be orthogonal and consequently the autocorrelation among the descriptors was checked and is given in the correlation matrix in Table 2.

Statistically significant bi-parametric correlations were obtained when one of the parameters (BAC, WA, J, Id) is combined with the indicator parameter. The models obtained are reported as under :

$$pIC_{50} = -0.060 (\pm 0.079) BAC + 3.926 (\pm 1.052) IR_3 + 4.978 \quad (1)$$

$$n = 14, R = 0.934, R^2 = 0.871, R^2_A = 0.848, S.E. = 0.402, F_{(2, 11)} = 37.292, Q = 2.323$$

$$pIC_{50} = -0.204 (\pm 0.686) WA + 3.693 (\pm 1.139) IR_3 + 5.777 \quad (2)$$

$$n = 14, R = 0.919, R^2 = 0.845, R^2_A = 0.816, S.E. = 0.442, F_{(2, 11)} = 29.915, Q = 2.079$$

Table 1. Biological activity and physico-chemical data of CYP26A1 MCF-7 assays inhibitory activities

Sr. No	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	X	Y	pIC ₅₀	Id	Pz	BAC	J	⁰ χ	¹ χ	² χ	log P	WA	IR ₃
1.	CH ₂ CH ₃	H		N	CH	5.346	4.483	36.14	3	1.449	15.648	11.348	9.847	4.647	4.553	0
2.	CH ₂ CH ₃	H		CH	N	5.301	4.483	36.14	3	1.449	15.648	11.348	9.847	4.647	4.553	0
3.	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	H		N	CH	4.124	4.586	37.97	4	1.421	16.355	11.848	10.227	5.107	4.808	0
4.	CH(CH ₃) ₂	H		N	CH	4.522	4.531	37.90	6	1.440	16.518	11.720	10.577	5.017	4.732	0
5.	CH(CH ₃) ₂	H		CH	N	4.124	4.531	37.90	6	1.440	16.518	11.720	10.577	5.017	4.732	0
6.	C(CH ₃) ₃	H		N	CH	4.769	3.797	39.86	11	1.440	17.441	12.021	11.636	5.627	4.873	0

Table-1 (contd.)

7.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	H		N	CH	4.346	4.592	39.72	7	1.405	17.225	12.204	11.068	5.637	5.013	0
8.	Cyclohexyl	H		N	CH	5.000	4.727	42.51	0	1.232	18.054	13.382	11.731	6.347	5.316	0
9.	C_6H_5	H		N	CH	5.154	4.727	42.51	0	1.232	18.054	13.382	11.731	5.027	5.316	0
10.	C_6H_5	H		CH	N	5.045	4.727	42.51	0	1.232	18.054	13.382	11.731	5.027	5.316	0
11.	<i>p</i> -Cl- C_6H_4	H		N	CH	4.522	4.716	44.34	2	1.215	18.924	13.776	12.353	5.627	5.542	0
12.	<i>p</i> -Cl- C_6H_4	H		CH	N	4.522	4.716	44.34	2	1.215	18.924	13.776	12.353	5.627	5.542	0
13.	H	Cl		CH	CH	5.154	4.468	35.05	2	1.486	14.941	10.810	9.678	2.480	4.264	0
14.		N	CH	8.301	4.690	44.69	10	1.279	18.640	13.280	11.357	3.375	5.732	1		

Table 2. Correlation matrix between biological activity and physico-chemical parameters

	pIC ₅₀	Id	Pz	BAC	J	WA	⁰ χ	¹ χ	² χ	log P	IR ₃
pIC ₅₀	1.000										
Id	0.130	1.000									
Pz	0.298	0.424	1.000								
BAC	0.287	-0.618	-0.077	1.000							
J	-0.195	-0.611	-0.927	0.439	1.000						
WA	0.354	0.482	0.990	-0.055	-0.914	1.000					
⁰ χ	0.202	0.354	0.990	-0.031	-0.899	0.974	1.000				
¹ χ	0.180	0.517	0.977	-0.269	-0.979	0.965	0.968	1.000			
² χ	0.010	0.228	0.932	-0.097	-0.865	0.882	0.962	0.931	1.000		
log P	-0.548	0.014	0.375	-0.126	-0.383	0.356	0.474	0.458	0.563	1.000	
IR ₃	0.916	0.161	0.393	0.486	-0.195	0.462	0.318	0.240	0.095	-0.458	1.000

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -0.162 (\pm 2.571) J + 3.524 (\pm 1.049) \text{IR}_3 + 4.984 \quad (3)$$

$$n = 14, R = 0.916, R^2 = 0.839, R^2_A = 0.810, \text{S.E.} = 0.450, F_{(2, 11)} = 28.650, Q = 2.035$$

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -0.074 (\pm 1.156) \text{Id} + 3.547 (\pm 1.042) \text{IR}_3 + 5.101 \quad (4)$$

$$n = 14, R = 0.916, R^2 = 0.839, R^2_A = 0.810, \text{S.E.} = 0.450, F_{(2, 11)} = 28.653, Q = 2.035$$

In all the above equations *n* is the number of compounds in the data set, *R* is the correlation coefficient, *R*² is the coefficient of determination, *R*²_A is the adjusted *R*², *S.E.* is the standard error of estimate, *F* is the variance ratio^{23,24} and *Q* is the quality of fit^{25,26}. In all the above models, the sign of the coefficients of parameters are negative which shows that less bulkier substituents with lesser branching should be preferred for modeling. The positive sign of coefficients of indicator parameter shows that [-CH(CH₂CH₃)₂] group has a positive influence on activity and should be retained at *R*₃ position in the future drug designing. The high values of *R*, *R*² and low values of *S.E.* indicate the statistical significance of the above mentioned models.

The significant equations obtained by using zero-, first- and second-order connectivity indices in combination with indicator parameter *IR*₃ are given as below :

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -0.078 (\pm 0.218) {}^0\chi + 3.658 (\pm 1.056) \text{IR}_3 + 6.110 \quad (5)$$

$$n = 14, R = 0.921, R^2 = 0.847, R^2_A = 0.820, \text{S.E.} = 0.438, F_{(2, 11)} = 30.553, Q = 2.102$$

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -0.042 (\pm 0.276) {}^1\chi + 3.575 (\pm 1.055) \text{IR}_3 + 5.285 \quad (6)$$

$$n = 14, R = 0.917, R^2 = 0.840, R^2_A = 0.811, \text{S.E.} = 0.448, F_{(2, 11)} = 28.941, Q = 2.046$$

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -0.086 (\pm 0.294) {}^2\chi + 3.565 (\pm 1.015) \text{IR}_3 + 5.720 \quad (7)$$

$$n = 14, R = 0.919, R^2 = 0.845, R^2_A = 0.816, \text{S.E.} = 0.442, F_{(2, 11)} = 29.901, Q = 2.079$$

The above equations show that the coefficient of different orders of molecular connectivity parameters (⁰χ, ¹χ, ²χ) are negative and this indicates that substituents with lesser branching should be preferred for future modeling. In these three models (5, 6 and 7), the coefficients of indicator parameters are positive implying that [-CH(CH₂CH₃)₂] group at *R*₃ position should be beneficial for anti-cancer activity.

The model obtained by using the combination of *Pz* with indicator parameter is as follows :

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -0.022 (\pm 0.089) \text{Pz} + 3.649 (\pm 1.104) \text{IR}_3 + 5.670 \quad (8)$$

$$n = 14, R = 0.918, R^2 = 0.843, R^2_A = 0.815, \text{S.E.} = 0.444, F_{(2, 11)} = 29.596, Q = 2.067$$

In the above equation, the negative coefficient of polarizability (*Pz*) implies that less polar group should be preferred. The positive sign of *IR*₃ has the same effect as discussed earlier. The combination of *log P* with indicator parameter gave the following model :

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -0.170 (\pm 0.293) \log P + 3.249 (\pm 1.081) \text{IR}_3 + 5.625 \quad (9)$$

$$n = 14, R = 0.927, R^2 = 0.859, R^2_A = 0.834, \text{S.E.} = 0.420, F_{(2, 11)} = 33.630, Q = 2.207$$

In model 9, the sign of coefficient of log P is negative implying that less hydrophobic group should be conducive for anti-cancer activity. In model number 9, the indicator parameter has once again positive coefficient.

All the models (eqs. 1 to 9) were found to be statistically significant on the basis of F_{test} . The calculated F values for all of them were found to be greater than F theoretical values [$F_{(2, 11)} = 3.98$]. On the basis of calculated statistical parameters, it is evident that model 1 is the best among all bi-parametric models discussed above. The Pogliani's quality factor Q is the ratio of correlation coefficient to its standard error of estimation i.e. $Q = R/S.E.$, thus higher the value of R and the lower the S.E., the greater will be the value of Q. The predictive power as determined by the Pogliani Q parameter for the model expressed by eq. (1) [$Q = 2.323$] confirms that this model has excellent statistics as well as excellent predictive power.

data set and hence these models can be termed as statistically significant.

Cross validation provides the values of PRESS, SSY and R^2_{cv} and PSE from which we can test the predictive power of the proposed model. The meanings of these cross-validated parameters are given as a footnote to the Table 4. It is argued that PRESS is a good estimate of the real predictive error of the model and if it is smaller than SSY the model predicts better than chance and can be considered as statistically significant. Furthermore, the ratio PRESS/SSY can be used to calculate approximate confidence intervals of prediction of new compound. To be a reasonable QSAR model PRESS/SSY should be smaller than 0.4 and for our models the value of this ratio which is smaller than 0.1 indicates that they are excellent models. Also, if PRESS value is transformed in a dimension less term by relating it to the initial sum of squares,

Table 3. Comparison between observed and predicted activities and their residual values

Sr. No.	pIC ₅₀ (Observed)	Predicted	Residual
1.	5.346	4.796	0.550
2.	5.301	4.796	0.505
3.	4.124	4.736	-0.612
4.	4.522	4.616	-0.094
5.	4.124	4.616	-0.492
6.	4.769	4.315	0.454
7.	4.346	4.555	-0.209
8.	5.000	4.977	0.023
9.	5.154	4.977	0.177
10.	5.045	4.977	0.068
11.	4.522	4.857	-0.335
12.	4.522	4.857	-0.335
13.	5.154	4.857	0.297
14.	8.301	8.301	0.000

Predicted and residual activity values for model 1 are given in Table 3. Predicted values are the calculated activities obtained from model 1 and the residual values are the difference between the observed biological activities and calculated activities. The plot of observed pIC₅₀ versus predicted pIC₅₀ for eq. (1) is shown in graph (Fig. 1) and the predicted R^2 was found to be fairly large.

Cross validation :

The cross validation analysis was performed using leave one out (LOO) method^{27,28}, in which one compound is removed from the data set and the activity is correlated using the rest of the data set. The cross-validated R^2 was found to be very close to the value of R^2 for the entire

Fig. 1. A plot showing comparison between observed and predicted pIC₅₀ values using eq. (1).

Table 4. Predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) and cross-validation parameters for the proposed models

Sr. No.	Model no.	n	R	1-R ²	PE	6PE	PRESS	SSY	PRESS/SSY	R ² _{cv}	PSE
1.	1.	14	0.934	0.127	0.033	0.198	1.780	12.068	0.147	0.852	0.356
2.	2.	14	0.919	0.155	0.041	0.246	2.151	11.698	0.183	0.816	0.391
3.	3.	14	0.916	0.160	0.042	0.252	2.230	11.618	0.191	0.808	0.398
4.	4.	14	0.916	0.160	0.042	0.252	2.230	11.618	0.191	0.808	0.398
5.	5.	14	0.921	0.151	0.040	0.240	2.113	11.736	0.180	0.820	0.388
6.	6.	14	0.917	0.159	0.042	0.252	2.211	11.637	0.189	0.810	0.397
7.	7.	14	0.919	0.155	0.041	0.246	2.151	11.697	0.183	0.816	0.391
8.	8.	14	0.918	0.157	0.041	0.246	2.170	11.678	0.185	0.814	0.393
9.	9.	14	0.927	0.140	0.037	0.222	1.946	11.902	0.163	0.836	0.372

PRESS : Predicted residual Sum of Squares.

SSY : Sum of the Squares of the response.

R²_{cv} : Overall Predictive ability.

PSE : Predictive Square error.

we obtain R²_{cv} i.e. the complement to the traces on of unexplained variance over the total variance. The PRESS and R²_{cv} have good properties. However, for practical purposes of end users the use of square root of PRESS/N, which is called predictive square error (PSE), is more directly related to the uncertainty of the predictions. The PSE values also support our results. The calculated cross-validated parameters confirm the validity of the models.

Predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) :

The predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE)²⁹ is yet another parameter used to decide the predictive power of the proposed models. We have calculated PE value of all the proposed models and they are reported in Table 4. It is argued that of

(i) R < PE, then correlation is not significant;

(ii) R > PE, several times (at least three times), then correlation is indicated; and if

(iii) R > 6PE, then the correlation is definitely good.

For all the models developed the condition R > 6PE and hence they can be said to have good predictive power.

On the basis of above discussions it may be said that for future drug designing in this series less bulkier, less polar substituents having lesser branching and less hydrophobic in nature should be preferred. The positive sign of coefficient of indicator parameter IR₃, clearly indicate that [-CH(CH₂CH₃)₂] should be beneficial towards the activity at R₃ position.

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